

HOW TO MOTIVATE KIDS TO LEARN MUSIC - TIPS AND TECHNIQUES TO MAINTAIN INTEREST AND DEVELOP SKILLS IN STUDENTS OF ALL AGES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to a pressing issue that many parents and teachers face: how to maintain children's interest in music and motivate them to practice regularly. The publication will consider various approaches and methods that will help develop musical abilities in children of different ages. It will also analyze why children lose interest in music and what factors help maintain motivation.

Key words: music education, children's motivation, musical abilities, child development, pedagogy, psychology.

In this article, we will discuss a common phenomenon - a child's loss of interest in music lessons. Music is a universal language that can enrich the life of every person. It develops creativity, improves memory, and forms a sense of rhythm and harmony. Many parents strive to instill a love of music in their children by sending them to classes at a music school or studio. However, it is not always easy to maintain a child's constant interest in music lessons. Why do children lose interest in music? In many cases, this is due to a lack of obvious achievements, the complexity of the material being studied, a low level of motivation, or the fact that music lessons are perceived by the child as uninteresting and monotonous.

Very often, the problem is that the parents' desire is not initially supported by the child's desire. Often, mothers and fathers want to realize their dreams and ambitions in their child. For example, a mother always wanted to play the piano, but it didn't work out, and now her child is studying piano at a music school. But does the child need it? Of course, learning music is great, but take a closer look: is the child interested in this instrument? Maybe he likes the violin or guitar more? Or maybe he has a clear, ringing voice and dreams of singing? It is very important to remember that your child should show at least a little initiative. The responsibility of parents is to support the child in his hobbies. In addition, many parents do not participate in the process and abstract themselves. Parental comments are often expressed as follows: "I'm not a musician, I can't figure it out and I don't understand anything!" or "It's his (her) choice, let him (her) decide whether to go or not!" Even without musical education, parents can participate in lessons, learning key points, and at home study assignments and simply be near the young musician, providing him with psychological support first and foremost. After all, it is nice to realize that parents instill a sense of responsibility in their children, are actively involved in the educational process and strive to provide support. And it is important to emphasize the fact that it happens that children have a temporary cooling off in their music lessons. And this is a completely natural stage that you just need to survive. The child has stopped approaching the instrument independently and loses interest after 5 minutes of lessons. These are completely normal phenomena! The reasons often lie in

excessive workload and high expectations from the teacher. As a result, a "lack of self-confidence" and apathy may arise. Vacations and weekends usually help to cope with these difficulties. Children need a break from constant interaction with teachers, clubs, numerous sections and tutors. As a result, they return to school with renewed energy.

It is also impossible to ignore the fact that a child can get tired. In one of his television interviews, Vladimir Spivakov shared his memories of how his father demanded that he repeat a musical passage as many times as there were matches in a box. As the matches ran out, he began to put them back, and his gifted son continued to "sharpen" the same passage many more times. It is not surprising that the future outstanding violinist and conductor had a strong desire to give up playing the violin forever. It should be noted that even such brilliant composers as Beethoven and Mozart experienced fatigue from intensive musical training in childhood. One of the main reasons for the reluctance to do anything is that people are susceptible to fatigue from work - even if they like it. Fatigue becomes almost inevitable when the work is performed regularly, is mandatory and is subject to evaluation. For children, such an imposed routine is especially difficult. In addition, the systematic evaluation of their efforts by the point system at school can cause emotional overload and lead to states of discomfort. It is necessary to realize that a young musician who devotes time to lessons while his peers are resting, receives marks several times a week and takes mini-exams (academic concerts and technical checks) every quarter. Sooner or later, he may begin to express dissatisfaction.

Based on the above, the question arises: "What to do?" It is necessary to look for methods to combat routine and act in two key directions:

1. A child's life should not be limited exclusively to music lessons. It is useful if he combines music lessons with other hobbies that are not subject to strict assessment. It is important to allocate time for communication with friends, active games, physical activity, choreography, reading, visiting theaters, zoos and other events.
2. Methods for optimizing and diversifying music lessons should be developed. However, we will talk about this later.

One of the important factors in maintaining a child's interest in music is motivation. Motivation is a fundamental factor that determines our behavior. It serves as the basis for our efforts to achieve planned goals and realize personal goals and ambitions. According to self-determination theory, motivation is divided into two main types: internal and external. Internal motivation is characterized by the desire to engage in an activity for one's own pleasure and satisfaction. In contrast, external motivation is determined by external factors, such as the desire to receive a reward or avoid negative consequences.

It all starts with the functioning of the brain. The brain is the control center of our body and plays a key role in regulating our behavior. Inside the brain is the reward system, which produces dopamine, a neurotransmitter that causes a feeling of pleasure when we do things we enjoy. When we experience pleasure, the brain releases dopamine, which creates motivation to repeat this behavior to achieve a similar feeling of pleasure. Motivation also depends on our beliefs and expectations. How we perceive ourselves and the task at hand can either increase or decrease our motivation. For example, if we have confidence that we can achieve a particular goal, the likelihood that we will be motivated to achieve it increases. On the other hand, if we doubt our abilities, our motivation can significantly weaken. Another aspect that influences motivation is the environment we find ourselves in. The environment, whether at work or in the educational process, can both promote and hinder our motivation. For example, a comfortable and inspiring environment can increase motivation, while a gloomy and uninteresting environment, such as negative coworkers, can decrease motivation. Social factors play a significant role in shaping motivation. The people

we associate with, such as peers, family members, and friends, can both help and hinder our motivation. When we are surrounded by supportive and inspiring individuals, we are more likely to achieve our goals. In contrast, having negative and critical people in our environment can decrease motivation.¹

There are various strategies and techniques that can help develop musical skills in children of different age groups. For children under one year old, listening to music for about 3 minutes at 30-second intervals is recommended. At this age, the voice of the parents is most effectively perceived, so songs or melodies performed by family members are preferable. For children aged 2–3 years, it is important to gradually form associations with music. In this process, it is useful to use children's musical compositions with expressive content. Listening to musical works should be organized in a calm environment, while parents need to be nearby. For children aged 3–4 years. They develop their musical abilities by watching TV programs and listening to music and songs from cartoons in the company of their parents. For children aged 5–6 years. At this age, musical perception begins to acquire a more conscious character. Children develop a culture of perceiving melodies, as well as the ability to analyze musical works. The child begins to remember information about musical groups and genres, which helps to form his individual preferences. Musical and didactic games help develop children's interest in music in an entertaining way, and also help master the basic principles of musical literacy. By mastering expressive singing techniques, a child learns to control his voice, develops the correct vocal technique, and develops memory, imagination, and musical ear. Theatrical activity is a method that helps develop the perception of musical images and the ability to independently convey them through movement. In addition, this approach activates the creative potential of each child. The choice of teaching methods is determined by the objectives of the lesson, the content of the educational material, the age of the students, and their level of training.

To maintain children's interest in music and encourage them to practice regularly, you can use the following tips:

1. Organize a music corner in your home. In this space, your child will be able to listen to music, participate in musical and educational games, and play children's musical instruments.
2. Music should not be viewed as a school subject. It is important that the child himself shows a desire to study music and does not perceive it as a mandatory course.
3. Allow your child to set his own schedule. Discuss with him whether he prefers to study immediately after school or in the evening, and whether he is willing to attend classes on weekdays or sacrifice part of the weekend.
4. Support your child during rehearsals. Try to be there during lessons: listen to him, ask questions about the piece he is learning, or ask him to teach you a few chords.
5. Choose music that your child likes. Ask your teacher if they can devote time to modern songs, or find lessons on YouTube together with your child.
6. Come up with various challenges. During home rehearsals, ask your child to complete some task or game.

In this article, we looked at various aspects of motivating children to take up music. We found that both external factors (home atmosphere, parental support, interesting teaching methods) and internal factors (the child's desire, sense of achievement, enjoyment of the process) play a key role. It is important to remember that each child is unique, and the approach to motivation should be individual. It is necessary to take into account their age,

¹Information taken from the site <https://dzen.ru/a/ZFQa1Kk4bW9SbF7F>

temperament, level of development, and personal interests.

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that music education is not only mastering the technique of playing an instrument, but also developing creative potential, emotional sphere and communication skills. By encouraging children to study music, we help them become more self-confident, develop their talents and reach new heights. Let music become for your children not just a lesson, but an exciting journey into the world of harmony and beauty!

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